

V.I. Tsymbalyuk¹,
I.A. Lurin¹,
V.O. Zhakhovskiy²,
V.G. Livinskiy²,
A.V. Shvets²

**PROVISION OF MEDICAL ASSISTANCE
TO MILITARY PERSONNEL AND CIVILIANS
IN CLINICAL INSTITUTIONS
OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY
OF MEDICAL SCIENCES
OF UKRAINE DURING THE ATO/JFO**

National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine¹
Hertsena str., 12, Kyiv, 04050, Ukraine
Ukrainian military medical academy²
Moskovska, 45/1, Kyiv, 01015, Ukraine
Національна академія медичних наук України¹
вул. Герцена, 12, Київ, 04050, Україна
Українська військово-медична академія²
вул. Московська, 45/1, Київ, 01015, Україна
e-mail: zhahovskiy-viktor@ukr.net

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Abstract. Provision of medical assistance to military personnel and civilians in clinical institutions of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine during the ATO/JFO. Tsymbalyuk V.I., Lurin I.A., Zhakhovskiy V.O., Livinskiy V.G., Shvets A.V. Purpose – analysis and generalization of the experience of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (NAMS) of Ukraine and its subordinate research institutions, with clinical units in their structure, on the provision of highly specialized medical care to the wounded, injured, injured and sick servicemen during the anti-terrorist operation and the operation of the Joint Forces (ATO/JFO), as well as the civilian population and internally displaced persons from the temporarily occupied territories. The object of the research is the health care system of military personnel. The subject of the research is the work of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine on the organization and provision of medical assistance to military personnel and civilians during the ATO/JFO. Research methods: bibliographic, statistical, analytical, systems approach. The NAMS of Ukraine and its subordinate research institutions, with clinical units in the structure, during the ATO/JFO took an active part in the provision of medical care to the wounded, injured, injured and sick servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations. The work of the NAMS of Ukraine in providing medical assistance to servicemen was multi-vector and was carried out in several directions: organizational, direct provision of medical care and its scientific support. Clinical institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine during the ATO/JFO did not stop providing highly specialized medical care to the civilian population of Ukraine, including internally displaced persons from the areas of the ATO/JFO. Thanks to the coordinated activities of the Presidium of the NAMS of Ukraine and its subordinate research institutions, a significant contribution has been made to the provision of highly specialized medical care to the wounded, injured and sick servicemen, as well as internally displaced persons from the temporarily occupied territories.

Реферат. Оказание медицинской помощи военнослужащим и гражданскому населению в клинических учреждениях Национальной академии медицинских наук Украины во время АТО/ООС. Цымбалюк В.И., Лурин И.А., Жаховский В.А., Ливинский В.Г., Швеца А.В. Цель – анализ и обобщение опыта работы Национальной академии медицинских наук (НАМН) Украины и подчиненных ей научно-исследовательских учреждений, в структуре которых имеются клинические подразделения, по оказанию высокоспециализированной медицинской помощи раненым, пораженным, травмированным и больным военнослужащим во время антитеррористической операции и операции Объединенных сил (АТО/ООС), а также гражданскому населению и внутренне перемещенным лицам из временно оккупированных территорий. Объект исследования – система охраны здоровья военнослужащих. Предмет исследования – работа НАМН Украины по организации и

оказанию медицинской помощи военнослужащим и гражданскому населению во время АТО/ООС. Методы исследования: библиографический, статистический, аналитический, системного подхода. НАМН Украины и подчиненные ей научно-исследовательские учреждения, в структуре которых имеются клинические подразделения, во время АТО/ООС приняли активное участие в оказании медицинской помощи раненым, пораженным, травмированным и больным военнослужащим ВС Украины и других военных формирований. Работа НАМН Украины в оказании медицинской помощи военнослужащим была многовекторной и велась по нескольким направлениям: организационное, непосредственное оказание медицинской помощи и её научное сопровождение. Клинические учреждения НАМН Украины во время АТО/ООС не прекращали оказывать высокоспециализированную медицинскую помощь гражданскому населению Украины, в том числе и вынужденным переселенцам из районов проведения АТО/ООС. Благодаря слаженной деятельности Президиума НАМН Украины и подчиненных ей научно-исследовательских учреждений сделан весомый вклад в оказание высокоспециализированной медицинской помощи раненым, пораженным травмированным и больным военнослужащим, а также внутренне перемещенным лицам из временно оккупированных территорий.

The fighting in eastern Ukraine has been going on for seven years, with numerous irreversible and sanitary losses both among the military and the civilian population of Ukraine. According to official data from the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (UNHCHR), during the entire period of the conflict, from April 14, 2014 to mid-2020, more than 40,000 people became victims of the military conflict [14]. During the war, about 4,100 Ukrainian servicemen and more than 3,000 civilians were killed, including 147 children, and a total of more than 13,000 people. Nearly 30,000 wounded, including more than 10,000 Ukrainian servicemen and about 7-9,000 civilians are among the victims of the war in eastern Ukraine.

Approximately 2 million residents of Donbass had to flee the war zone, among them almost 1.5 million people were forced to seek refuge in other regions of Ukraine. Most officially registered migrants live in Donetsk region – 510.8 thousand people, in Luhansk region – 280.6 thousand people and in Kharkiv region – 134.1 thousand people, in Kyiv – 159.6 thousand migrants.

The armed conflict in eastern Ukraine, which began as an anti-terrorist operation (ATO) and was transformed into a Joint Forces (JFO) operation, was the first serious test for the medical services of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations to provide medical care to servicemen with combat surgical and therapeutic pathology, as well as with combat trauma and post-traumatic mental disorders.

The military medical services of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations provide medical assistance to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen directly on the battlefield, at the first and second levels of medical support and conduct medical evacuations. At the same time, due to the lack of their own forces and resources, civilian health care facilities, including research state institutions (SI) of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (NAMS) of Ukraine

are widely involved in providing specialized and highly specialized medical care to servicemen [8, 9].

The procedure for involving civilian health care facilities in providing medical care to servicemen is determined by the Order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine “Some issues of medical care for servicemen of junior enlisted, overbearing ones and police officers participating in the anti-terrorist operation and implementation of measures to ensure national security and defense, repulse and deterrence of armed aggression of the Russian Federation in Donetsk and Luhansk regions” and a joint order of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine and the Ministry of Health of Ukraine “On determining the mechanism of secondary (specialized) and tertiary (highly specialized) medical assistance to servicemen participating in the anti-terrorist operation and the implementation of measures to ensure national security and defense, repulse and deterrence of armed aggression of the Russian Federation and/or in the context of martial law or state of emergency” [1, 6].

In accordance with these regulations, 1,001 hospital beds in 27 subordinate clinical institutions, including 601 surgical beds and 400 therapeutic beds have been devoted by NAMS of Ukraine to provide highly specialized medical care to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen.

The work of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine on providing medical care to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations and law enforcement agencies formed in accordance with the law, junior enlisted, overbearing ones and police officers participating in the ATO/JFO and the implementation of measures to ensure national security and defense, repulse and deterrence of armed aggression of the Russian Federation in Donetsk and Luhansk regions, as well as the civilian population, was multi-vector and was conducted in the following main areas:

first – the participation of the Presidium of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine

in the organizational and methodological guidance of the organization of medical care for wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen;

secondly – providing high-tech highly specialized medical care to the most severely wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen in need of long-term and complex treatment by the specialists of clinical institutions of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine, who are directly involved in the system of medical evacuation measures troops, as well as the civilian population in the areas of ATO/JFO and internally displaced persons from the temporarily occupied territories;

thirdly – collection, analysis and generalization of the experience gained in providing medical care to the wounded, injured, traumatized and sick during hostilities in the areas of ATO/JFO as well as search and scientific substantiation of modern approaches to diagnosis and treatment and development of new methods of medical care delivery.

Unfortunately, the coverage of many issues related to the provision of medical care to servicemen and civilians in the clinical institutions of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine during the ATO/JFO is presented in fragments in the available sources of information. And first of all it concerns mainly the second direction of activity of NAMS of Ukraine. Therefore, in our opinion, the analysis of the provision of high-tech highly specialized medical care to wounded, injured and sick servicemen, as well as the civilian population in the ATO/JFO areas and internally displaced persons from the temporarily occupied territories is topical.

The purpose of the work is to analyze and summarize the experience of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (NAMS) of Ukraine and its subordinate research institutions, which include clinical units, in provision of highly specialized medical care to wounded, injured and sick servicemen during the anti-terrorist operation and the Joint Forces (ATO/JFO) operation, as well as to the civilian population and internally displaced persons from the temporarily occupied territories.

Object of research: the system of health protection of servicemen and civilians.

Subject of research: the work of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine on the organization and provision of medical care to servicemen and civilians during the ATO/JFO.

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

Regulations on national security and health care delivery in Ukraine, publications in open scientific sources were used. Research methods: bibliographic, statistical, analytical, system approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the very beginning of the ATO in eastern Ukraine and during the JFO the clinical institutions of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine took an active part in providing medical care to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations. In addition, all this time the clinical institutions of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine have not stopped providing highly specialized medical care to the population of Ukraine, including internally displaced persons from the areas ATO/JFO. Their work was organized and carried out in accordance with the legislation, regulations of Ukraine on health care and the Statute of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine [4, 7, 12].

The procedure for organizing cooperation between the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine and the medical support bodies of the Armed Forces of Ukraine in providing medical care to servicemen is defined in the “Methodological recommendations for organizing the work of civilian health care institutions for providing secondary (specialized) and tertiary (highly specialized) care delivery to the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations” [3], and is detailed in the monograph “Unified Medical Space and Military Medicine” [2]. In order to ensure the readiness of scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine to provide medical care to war victims and the proper organization of their work to implement the Decision of the Verkhovna Rada Committee on Health “On taking urgent measures to improve the organization of medical care delivery to population and participants of anti-terrorist operation” [5] and the Decree of the President of Ukraine “On urgent measures to ensure state security” [11] an Order of the NAMS of Ukraine “On urgent measures to provide medical care by medical facilities of the NAMS of Ukraine” was issued [10].

Also in pursuance of the Order of the Ministry of Health (MH) of Ukraine “On additional measures to ensure the functioning of health care facilities in a special period and overcoming the consequences of an emergency situation of the state level of social and military nature” [13] a number of orders governing the activities of subordinate research institutions in a special period were issued. To implement these orders in the NAMS of Ukraine:

- an operational headquarters was set up to provide assistance to the wounded in the anti-terrorist operation zone;

- mobile medical brigades have been formed, which are ready to respond to care delivery to the wounded with vehicles assigned to them, equipped with medical equipment, medical devices and medicines;

- schedules of shifts of mobile medical teams are developed and schemes of round-the-clock notification are approved;

- a reserve of volunteer doctors was formed, ready to go to the anti-terrorist operation zone to strengthen medical facilities of the second level (over 77 surgeons, traumatologists, anesthesiologists);

- cooperation agreements on the provision of highly specialized high-tech medical care to servicemen were concluded between the NAMS of Ukraine and the Military Medical Department of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, the Security Service of Ukraine, the Department of Medical Support and Rehabilitation of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, Center of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, Central Clinical Hospital of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, Central Hospital of the Military Medical Department of the Security Service of Ukraine, Central Clinical Hospital of the State Tax Service of Ukraine and Central Hospital of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine.

In order to regulate the work of the NAMS of Ukraine on providing medical care to wounded, injured and sick servicemen, and internally displaced persons within the medical and organizational department of the NAMS of Ukraine, a department for mobilization and medical care was set up, later it was reorganized into the sector of organization of medical care for victims in the ATO zone (hereinafter - the Sector). Its main tasks are to provide highly specialized medical care to servicemen and citizens of Ukraine who suffered in the areas of anti-terrorist operation, to monitor the creation and implementation of scientific developments, guidelines, information letters, printed scientific papers on the provision of highly specialized medical care, assistance to victims of the anti-terrorist operation, as well as coordination of interaction and combination of efforts of specialists of scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine with medical services of military formations for effective and timely provision of highly specialized medical care.

In order to unify and standardize approaches to the organization and provision of medical care to ATO participants by the NAMS of Ukraine, a "Roadmap for providing medical care to ATO participants in scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine" (Road Map) has been developed. The

Roadmap program provides for the organization and undergoing of outpatient counseling, inpatient, rehabilitation, psychological, rehabilitation and other types of highly specialized medical care for servicemen and employees of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations involved in ATO/JFO.

In pursuance of the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine "On additional measures to ensure the functioning of health care facilities in a special period and overcoming the consequences of a state of emergency of social and military nature" [13] and in accordance with resolutions and orders of the Presidium of NAMS of Ukraine, in the clinics of 24 scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine in Kyiv, Lviv, Odessa and Kharkiv from 10 to 30 percent of the bedspace was devoted for wounded, injured, traumatized and sick, a total of 550 beds (Table 1).

In these clinical research institutions, specialized teams have been set up to provide emergency medical care to victims as directly in 24-hour duty of highly qualified specialists and round-the-clock reception of victims in need of urgent medical care. In some clinical research institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine, specialized centers and departments of combat trauma have been established to provide highly specialized medical care to ATO/JFO participants. In addition, the necessary stock of medicines, sets of medical instruments, blood and blood substitutes, drugs for anti-shock therapy, sterile solutions, sutures and dressings, contrast agents and other medical devices has been created.

In some clinical scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine, specialized centers and departments of combat trauma have been established to provide highly specialized medical care to ATO participants, namely:

SI "Institute of Pathology of the Spine and Joints named after Professor M.I. Sitenko" – 20 beds;

SI "Institute of Traumatology and Orthopedics" – 20 beds;

SI "Institute of General and Emergency Surgery named after VT Zaitsev" – a department of shock, trauma and military field surgery with 20 beds was established;

SI "Institute of Occupational Medicine named after YI Kundiev" – a department of medical-psychological and psycho-physiological rehabilitation of victims in the anti-terrorist operation with post-traumatic stress disorders was established with 40 beds;

SI "Institute of Neurology, Psychiatry and Narcology" – "Rehabilitation Center for ATO participants" with 30 beds.

Table 1

Number of stationary beds in research institutions of NAMS of Ukraine devoted to medical care delivery to the wounded, injured traumatized and sick servicemen due to ATO/JFO

N	Name of research institution	Number of beds
1.	National Research Center "Institute of Cardiology named after Academician MD Strazhesko"	20
2.	SI "Institute of Otolaryngology named after Professor OS Kolomiychenko"	30
3.	SI "Institute of Neurosurgery named after Academician AP Romodanov"	35
4.	SI "National Institute of Cardiovascular Surgery named after MM Amosov"	10
5.	SI "Institute of Traumatology and Orthopedics"	20
6.	SI "Institute of Urology"	15
7.	SI "National Institute of Surgery and Transplantology named after OO Shalimo"	50
8.	SI "National Institute of Tuberculosis and Pulmonology named after FG Janovski »	15
9.	SI "Scientific and Practical Center for Neuroradiology"	5
10.	SI "Institute of Pediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynecology named after OM Lukyanova"	20
11.	SI "Institute of Gerontology"	20
12.	SI "National Research Center for Radiation Medicine"	30
13.	SI "Institute of Endocrinology and Metabolism named after VP Komissarenko"	10
14.	SI "Institute of General and Emergency Surgery named after VT Zaitsev, NAMS of Ukraine"	25
15.	SI "Institute of Medical Radiology named after SP Grigoriev"	40
16.	SI "Institute of Neurology, Psychiatry and Addiction"	30
17.	SI "Institute of Child and Adolescent Health"	50
18.	SI "Institute of Pathology of the Spine and Joints named after Professor MI Sitenko »	20
19.	SI "National Institute of Therapy named after LT Malaya"	25
20.	SI "Institute of Dermatology and Venereology"	30
21.	SI "Institute of Gastroenterology"	5
22.	SI "Institute of Dentistry"	10
23.	SI "Institute of Ophthalmology and Tissue Therapy named after VP Filatov"	45
24.	SI "Institute of Blood Pathology and Transfusion Medicine"	10
	Together	550

As of the beginning of 2020, 16,680 servicemen – participants of hostilities were consulted in the clinics of scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine, 4,326 of them were hospitalized (Table 2).

Table 2

Indicators of performance of clinical settings of the NAMS of Ukraine on providing medical care to servicemen – participants of ATO/JFO

Years	Number of consulted servicemen- participants of ATO/JFO		Number of hospitalized servicemen- participants of ATO/JFO		Number of consulted and treated in other health care settings	
	indicator over the year	since the beginning of ATO	indicator over the year	since the beginning of ATO	indicator over the year	since the beginning of ATO
2015	974	974	608	608	765	765
2016	5 002	5 976	1 654	2 262	406	1 171
2017	3 507	9 483	587	2 849	16	1 187
2018	2 673	12 156	557	3 406	29	1 216
2019	3 554	15 710	736	4 142	8	1 224
2020 (as on 01.05.2020)	970	16 680	184	4 326	-	1 224

The largest number of wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen - participants of the ATO/JFO were consulted and treated inpatiently in the institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine in 2016 (5,002 patients were consulted, 1,654 patients were inpatiently treated).

Among the clinical research institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine, the largest number of wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen - members of the ATO /JFO was consulted in the State Institution "Institute of Neurosurgery named after Academician AP Romodanov" (3,779 people), State Institution "Institute of Traumatology and Orthopedics" (2,596 people) and State Institution "Institute of Otolaryngology named after Professor OS Kolomiychenko" (2,087 people).

In accordance with the concluded agreements on cooperation between the NAMS of Ukraine and the National Military Medical Clinical Center MMCH" of the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, the Central Hospital of the Military Medical Department of the Security Service of Ukraine, the Central Clinical Hospital of the State Tax Service of Ukraine, specialists of the NAMS of Ukraine visited these health care facilities and other military medical facilities, including those close to combat areas, to

provide advisory and highly specialized high-tech medical care to wounded servicemen, a total of 1,224 people were consulted.

If there were medical indications, patients who needed highly specialized medical care were sent for hospitalization to specialized scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine. Most of the wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen - participants of the ATO/JFO were treated inpatiently in the State Institution "Institute of Traumatology and Orthopedics" (1,091 persons), the State Institution "Institute of Occupational Medicine named after Yul Kundiev" (846 people), SI" Institute of Neurosurgery named after Academician AP Romodanov" 657 people), State Institution "Institute of Otolaryngology named after Professor OS Kolomiychenko" (447 people), State Institution "National Institute of Surgery and Transplantology named after OO Shalimov" (165 people).

Also during the ATO/JFO in the polyclinic departments of clinical research institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine 176,611 civilian patients from Donetsk and Luhansk regions were consulted and provided medical care, and 58,872 people were treated in the hospital (Table 3).

**Number of patients consulted and treated in outpatient
and inpatient departments of research institutions of NAMS of Ukraine**

Years	Consulted and treated in outpatient settings			Treated in inpatient settings		
	regions		total	regions		total
	Donetsk	Luhansk		Donetsk	Luhansk	
2014	23 140	8 564	31 704	16 447	3 640	20 087
2015	17 880	11 815	29 695	6 386	3 252	9 638
2016	18 445	10 555	29 000	6 314	3 281	9 595
2017	18 005	9 981	27 986	6 114	2 997	9 111
2018	18 953	10 066	29 019	754	503	1 257
2019	18 646	10 561	29 207	6 241	2 943	9 184
Total	115 069	61 542	176 611	42 256	16 616	58 872

Armed conflict and ongoing hostilities in eastern Ukraine have revealed another nationwide health problem, namely the urgent need for medical, medical, psychological and social rehabilitation of combatants and other victims of war. The existence of problems in this area of rehabilitation medicine was officially confirmed in December 2015 by the WHO Evaluation Mission and the International Society for Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine.

In order to solve them, specialists of scientific institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine have developed methods of diagnosis and comprehensive treatment of patients using drug treatment, psychotherapy and physiotherapy procedures. In cooperation with scientists of the Ukrainian Military Medical Academy (UMMA) and the National Research Center “Institute of Cardiology named after Academician MD Strazheska” laid the foundations of medical and psychological rehabilitation in our country, which is reflected in the collective monograph “Stress-associated health disorders under conditions of armed conflict”.

In 2018, an intersectoral project was launched, which is based on a combination of efforts of the NAMS of Ukraine, UMMA and health care facilities of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine on basic research into contusion and its consequences. The obtained results are unique, because the developed technologies of restoration of lost cognitive func-

tions, memory, attention, mental capacity, taking into account the micro-social, family component of the processes of readaptation of persons with post-concussion syndrome are extremely important for effective medical, psychological and social rehabilitation of veterans.

On the basis of the clinic of occupational diseases of the State Institution “Institute of Occupational Medicine named after YuI Kundiev” in November 2014, a department of medical-psychological and psycho-physiological rehabilitation of ATO participants with 40 beds was established, in which more than 850 patients were treated. The department instituted 2 positions of psychotherapist and one position of medical psychologist.

Also, in order to provide qualified medical and psychological care to patients, an Agreement on Cooperation between the State Institution “Institute of Occupational Medicine named after YuI Kundiev” of NAMS of Ukraine and SI “Institute of Psychology named after GS Kostyuk” of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine was concluded, according to which 20 highly qualified certified psychologists are involved in the rehabilitation process on a volunteer basis, who have scientific degrees and experience in military psycho-trauma using modern psychotherapeutic methods.

“The Rehabilitation Center for ATO Participants has been operating at the Institute of Neurology,

Psychiatry and Narcology since 2014 as a coordination and functional unit that provides optimal and rational use of its own human and material resources for rehabilitation of ATO/JFO participants with the involvement of resources of other institutions. The center provides medical, psychological, psychiatric and neurological assistance to participants and victims of hostilities in the areas of ATO/JFO, performs research on these topics. SE "Institute of Neurology, Psychiatry and Narcology carries out these scientific developments on the basis of its own institution and the Military Medical Clinical Center of the Northern Region, develops and proposes methods of treatment and rehabilitation, issues methodological recommendations, information letters and other scientific publications dedicated to the issues of diagnosis, treatment and prevention of medical and psychological consequences of hostilities in modern conditions, socio-pedagogical and psychological assistance to families with children during military conflicts, etc.

On the basis of the Ukrainian Research Institute of Social and Forensic Psychiatry and Addiction of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine in cooperation with the State Institution "Institute of Otolaryngology named after Professor OS Kolomyichenko" there was established the Center for Medical and Psychological Rehabilitation, which is a public association that operates with the support and under the auspices of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine, NAMS of Ukraine and the National Expert Commission for the Protection of Public Morality. The main tasks of the Center are to provide counseling psychological and psychiatric, medical, social and legal assistance to victims of emergencies, which facilitates their rapid medical and psychological rehabilitation and resocialization in society.

Thus, the paper analyzes and summarizes the experience of the National Academy of Medical Sciences (NAMS) of Ukraine in providing highly specialized medical care to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen during the anti-terrorist operation and the Joint Forces operation (ATO/JFO), as well as civilians and internally displaced persons from the temporarily occupied territories, which testifies to the important participation of its subordinate research institutions, in the structure of which

there are clinical units, and medical practitioners on the basis of a single medical space of Ukraine.

CONCLUSIONS

1. NAMS of Ukraine and its subordinate research institutions with clinical units in the structure took an active part in providing medical care to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations during the ATO/JFO.

2. The work of the NAMS of Ukraine on providing medical care to wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations was multi-vector and was conducted in the following main areas:

- participating in the organizational and methodological management of the organization of medical care for servicemen;

- providing high-tech highly specialized medical care to the most severely wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen who need long-term and complex treatment;

- collection, analysis and generalization of the gained experience in providing medical care to the wounded, injured, traumatized and sick during hostilities in the areas of ATO/JFO, as well as search for and scientific substantiation of modern approaches to diagnosis and treatment and development of new methods of medical care.

3. During the ATO/JFO the clinical institutions of the NAMS of Ukraine did not stop providing highly specialized medical care to the civilian population of Ukraine, as well as organized its provision to patients from Donetsk and Luhansk regions and internally displaced persons from temporarily occupied territories in the inpatient and outpatient departments.

4. Thanks to the coordinated activities of the NAMS of Ukraine and its subordinate research institutions, a significant contribution was made to the medical support of the Armed Forces of Ukraine and other military formations in providing highly specialized medical care and treatment of wounded, injured, traumatized and sick servicemen.

Conflict of interest. The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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СПИСОК ЛІТЕРАТУРИ

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